

ISSN 0975-4067

KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series
Vol.XVI.Book.I-IV

January - December 2024

किरणावली
Sanskrit Research Foundation
Thiruvananthapuram

ISSN 0975-4067

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T.C 39/37

Thiruvananthapuram-36

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ISSN 0975-4067

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14576256>

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

A Peer-Reviewed Research Journal

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14633507>

Vrikshayurveda Literature - A Review

Dr. K.Murali¹

Abstract

As a science of life Ayurveda considers all living beings under its purview. Its approach and application in plants is conceived as virkshayurveda which has a long history of genesis and development. Beginnings of agriculture in India can be traced to Indus Valley Civilization. The developments later periods are well illustrated in Vedas. The same pace of furtherance is maintained in post Vedic periods also. This very well depicted in the texts of Brahmanas. Puranas are rich in the status of plant life and cultivation. Encyclopedic works like Brihatsamhitha and Vishnudharmothara-purana are important sources of Vrikshayurveda of those periods. Exclusive texts on the subject such as Kashyapiya-krishi-geethi, krishi-parashara, upavana-vinoda true evidence of the Ancient Indian Plant Science. A short review of the treatises is the content of this article.

Introduction

Ayurveda as a science of life envisages the well being of all the life forms. Diseases are affected not humans alone but plants and animals also. Man cared himself first. Later he/she understood that health is a totality of well being of the whole environment. It was also observed that growth and development of plants and animals are affected in several ways. Man tried to apply the same principles in flora and fauna, appropriate to the particular body. The observations and effective experimentations were documented during the course of the time. This paved the way to the genesis of specific knowledge system called Vrikshayurveda (VA). This knowledge system can be defined as the practical understanding of life and growth and

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cultivation of plants used for food, medicine and gardening. VA has very long history. It is elaborated through many books written in various centuries. This article is a short review of the literature available on VA.

Indus Valley Civilization

Though there was agriculture during the periods of Indus Valley civilization, it was limited by several reasons. One among these is that iron was not invented at that period which was an impediment in the production of effective instruments. Still, we have evidences for the cultivation of a variety of crops, such as wheat, barley, cotton, cereals, dates, etc. It is interesting to note that they were the first to cultivate cotton. Domestication of animals like cows, buffalo, sheep, goats, etc. was supportive of agriculture. Buffaloes were used to plough fields and transport goods. As the Indus script is not deciphered so far, our knowledge on their thoughts and observations are very limited.

Vedas

Since Vedas are the one among the earliest documents of human thought, traces of VA can be found in these vast range of Vedic literature(1500-500B.C.)

Life in Vedic times was in and around nature. Plants were the source not only for food but many other needs. Materials for housing, utensils and several instruments, clothing-all were derived from plants. Agriculture made people observe plants very closely. Rearing of domesticated animals and their feeds also gave an opportunity for the observation of the fauna. Some of the santhi-karmas (rituals) are named after plants may be because of their use in the procedure. Amritha (*Tinosporia cordifolia* Willd.), gayathri (*Acacia catechu*), aintri (*Baccopa monnieri* Linn.), aparajitha (*Clitoria ternatea* Linn.) and abhaya (*Terminalia chebula* Retz.) are examples. Mahabala was the name of a devatha later it was attributed to a plant (*Sida spinosa* Linn.). Names of sages like Muchukunda were given to trees (*Pterospemumsuberifolium* Linn.) in later period. Likewise, some trees like karanja (*Pongamiapinnata* Linn.), aralu (*Ailanthus excelsa*) etc. named after rakshasas (demons). Names of places were also

chosen after plants. So, there is varanavati (?), karaskara (*Strychnos nux-vomica* Linn.), shigru (*Moringa oleifera*) etc.

Growth and development of plant were also studied by Vedic scholars. Earth is the mother and environment is the father for a plant. There is specific habitat for each plant. Water and heat are necessary for the growth. The life process in herbs is also described Rigveda.

Parts of herbs are well narrated. There was an understanding on the useful part of the plant. Kanda (stem), shunga (bud), parva (branch), pathra (leaf), pushpa (flower), phala (fruit), moola (root) are common parts used for medicine. Probably the enquiry into the therapeutically effective part led to the study of morphology of a plant. The classification of fauna as apushpa and sapushpa (without and with flower) is also very interesting. Brihadaranyaka-upanishad compares the parts of a plant with that of a man.

Also, there are narrations of habitat, collection, mode of action and classification of plants though not in a very systematic way.

Brahmanas represent the post-Vedic literature. These contain explanations of mantras and hymns from the Vedas, teachings of legends illustrated by the myths, information about the performance of rituals, as well as some philosophy. Vedas, consist of two parts: the Samhita and the Brahmana. There exist one or more Brahmanas attached to each Veda. After several centuries of oral transmission, these Brahmanas are assumed to have been coded between 900–700 BCE. The word 'Brahmana' literally means 'explanations of sacred knowledge or doctrine.' Brahmanic literature clearly reflects the socio-cultural life of those ages.

A farming technique during those periods involved both cattle rearing and agriculture which is called integrated farming. Cattle were counted as a symbol of wealth in the Brahmanic days as they were also used for labour. They could domesticate many animals associated with agricultural activity. Pashu is a common term to denote animals. Gramyapashu is the domesticated animal and aranyapashu is the wild one. A person having cattle had high esteem in the society.

Vedic people could observe the animals from birth to death including their eating habits and other behaviourism. They used for ploughing the very first one in the agricultural activity. The 'anna' (food) is synonymous to 'krishi'(agriculture). Anna is not human consumption alone; it is an offering in sacrifices also. Relation between a plant and a particular season was well identified during these times. It was noted that plants perish when grains become ripe. There is a reference on 'langala' plough shaped timber used to dig the soil.

Ayurveda and Vrikshayurveda

Ayurveda was evolved probably in later Vedic periods. Theory of tridosha was developed probably during Upanishadic periods. With this, the functions of the human body became well explained. Abnormal changes in the body could be interpreted with this theory. Bodily effects of food, medicines were explained. How the causative factors of illness make one ill was also expounded rationally. More and more herbal plants were identified to be effectively used in treatment. But there are no direct references on VA in Ayurvedic texts. This is because nomenclature, morphology, habitat and properties were of importance in Ayurveda. Cultivation of medicinal plants was not of any need as these were available in abundance. But when the theories of Ayurveda were also applied in the field of cultivation, there emerged a distinct system, VA. Another important matter in this context is that those were traditionally engaged in agriculture, had the know-how of cultivation which was continuously under modification. Documentation of these were theorized to form VA.

It is not clear when the knowledge of agriculture was systematized to form VK. This knowledge system follows the principles of Ayurveda as indicated by the name. So, its documentation was initiated only after the evolvement of Ayurveda. It is generally considered that the system of Ayurveda was originated during Upanishadic period (1500-1000BCE). *Agnivesha-samhitha* was written in this period. Its redacted version *Charakasamhitha* is available now which belongs to second century. VK texts evolved in later period probably in the second or third century of Christian era, though it was in practice

much earlier. Authoring texts obviously involves theorization of practices. There are no references of VA in Ayurvedic texts. But dosha theory is well utilised in VA; both in the management of plant disease and constitutional analysis.

Puranas

The references of agriculture in **Ramayana** are also noteworthy. In the description of Ayodhya, there are mentions of amravana (mango groves). Sala-vriksha (palm trees) are planted as boundaries. Shali (rice) was cultivated in levelled lands. Valmeeki beautifully illustrates Agasthayshrama in Aranyakanda, with specifically naming trees, grasses, different cereals, fruiting plants etc. The name Seetha literally means a furrow. In Vedas, Seetha is Goddess of fertility. During the conversation at the forest, Rama asks Bharatha whether he properly maintains the irrigational facilities for agriculture. All these evidence that knowledge of VA was advanced to from a system of agriculture which was become an integral part of administration.

Pieces of information in puranas and ithihas as are also very captivating. They are not just stories or legends of this time. There are discussions and conversations on various subjects. These clearly show the prevailing and emerging knowledge systems. In **Mahabharatha** the debate between Bhrigu and Bharadvaja on the existence of life in plants is an example. Panchabhutha structure of plant body, organs present in them with their functions are unveiled during the argument. The description of dandakaranya is with a vivid narration of the co-existence of flora and fauna. Same picturisation can be found when Valmiki illustrates the trees in the hermitage of Sage Agasthya. All these evidence that people of those periods identified the plants with their morphological features. An awareness of ecology is also well reflected in these writings. Explanation given in Mahabharatha, to the term 'padapa' (that which drinks through the foot ie. roots) clearly shows the understanding of the nourishment of plants.

Vishnudharmottarapurana is an upapurana of brhaddharma-purana. It is a text with many subjects like the art of painting, and iconography etc. In this text also, one chapter is devoted

for vrikshayurveda. Many of the verses are similar to that of Brihatsamhitha. While planting trees a prioritising is suggested. Preference is given to fruiting and medicinal plants. Neem, Ashoka, Amra and Panasa are examples. Auspiciousness is another criterion for selecting plants.

Arthasastra a text on statecraft and politics details administrative steps necessary in the field of agriculture. Author Kautilya (321-296 BC) Minister to Chandragupta Maurya actually compiles the methods of ruling prevailing in those periods. Varta is the term used for agriculture, cattle breeding and trade during the times. Seethadhyaksha is the name suggested by Kautilya, for the head of the irrigation department. Importance of ploughing is stressed Kautilya to make the soil good in texture. Weather forecast also gained significance in predicting the harvest. Right time for sowing is very much stressed by Arthasastra. Sali (transplant rice), Virlu (direct sown rice), tila (Sesame), millets should be sown at the commencement of rain. Pulses are to be sown in the middle of season. Safflower, linseed mustard, barley, wheat are to be sown later. Similarly, the land areas ideal for the cultivation of each plant are also suggested by Kautilya. All these suggest that agricultural practices based on VA were prevalent during those periods.

Brihatsamhitha is a 6th-century encyclopaedia compiled by Varāhamihira. His nativity is the present-day Ujjain. In the work also a few chapters are devoted for VA. The author's area of expertise is Jyothisha. But this samhitha contains a wide variety of subjects. One commentary written by Utpala is also available. Total content of the book categorised as anga (section) and upanga (subsection). Anga discusses mainly Jyothisha and upanga other topics. It is interesting to note that Varāhamihira does not discuss many traditional topics which he considers legendary and unscientific. The poetic skill of the author is well reflected in the book. Nealy sixty-three different metres are used in Brihathasamhitha.

The chapter Krishi-vikalpa deals with subjects related to agriculture- selection of land, types of soil seasons for sowing particular seeds, importance of irrigation, and necessity of

ploughing, harvesting, and methods of storage. Importance of crop rotation was recognized. Fertilization to increase yield and pest control are other subjects dealt with. The basics of VA are the content of next chapter. Here classification of plants, seed selection, planting methods, pruning, grafting, propagation, and transplantation are narrated. There are advices on plant diseases and remedies. Dakargala are the methods to identify underground water. Cow dung (gomaya), bhasma (ashes), pinyaka (oil cakes), asthikshara (bone meal), samyoga (compost) are good fertilizers according to Varahamihira. In addition to these, he suggests specific manures for various trees and plants.

Exclusive Texts of Vrikshayurveda

One of the earliest original books on agriculture is **Kashyapeya-krishi-sukti**. The manuscript was found in Adayar Library, Chennai. The date of the manuscript belongs to early decades of Nineteenth Century. It was translated into English by G. Wojtilla 1985 which was published from Hungary. The currently available text is the one translated by Sri. S.M. Ayachit. It contains more than one thousand and five hundred verses divided into seventeen sections.

We don't know exactly who Kashyapa is. Myth logically he is one among the Sapta-rishies. There are references on him in Rigveda and Brihadaranya Upanishad. This venerated sage appears in some of the Buddhist texts also. In Mahabharatha, Kashyapa is a toxicologist. There is a dialogue between him and Thakshaka which appears in Adiparva. Another text attributed to this sage is Kashyapa-samhitha, the subject matter of which is balachikitsa (child care). Some scholars link the name Kashmir to Kashyapa. In the history of Sree Lanka also we find another Kashyapa a king who ruled the country 473-495 C.E. The author of Kashyapeyakraishisukti can be one acharya from the race (gothra) of Kashyapa. Sukti literally means 'good saying'.

The first part of the text titled as *shashtrapadeshakrama* is introductory in nature. Responsibility of the King in maintaining agriculture in the country is highlighted. Divinity is attributed to earth. Vishnu in kurmavathara (incarnation of tortoise) retrieved the earth. The synonyms ratnagarbha, vasundhara denotes the

treasures that earth contains. The term medini means fertile. It is the earth that sustains all living beings. Out of all the virtues earth have the most significant one is the production of grains and other vegetables. Next section contains classification of land. Characteristics of the ideal land for prosperity are described through several verses. Also, there are lands particularly suited to specific plants. These are identified enabling selective cultivation. Soil examination is interesting information in this section. This is done by smell, taste, turbidity etc. According to the water retaining potential or water content of the soil it is divided as apeethasalila and peethodaka. Particular plants living there, give the indications for this identification. An officer appointed by the King should do the tests and declare the land as fertile or not. Construction of water reservoirs is also an important duty of the rulers. Each village should have a water reservoir. Construction should be deep enough to hold required water and also with firm ridges. Not the plants alone but birds, reptiles and other animals are happy if there is a good water reservoir. These are to be inspected periodically by an officer for their proper maintenance and efficiency. Tapping the water from river is the content of the fourth part of Kashyapeeyakrishisukthi. Kulya (canal) has to be built to make the water reach the kshethra (field). Width and depth of these canals are also suggested. While moving further from the reservoir the main canal may get divided into smaller ones. Thus, dry lands can also be made fertile. Kashyapa highlights the social significance and collective participation necessary in agriculture. People of all castes under the leadership of King earnestly work hard for every aspect of this activity. Sudras are to be employed for physical work. Like the unity observed among the birds, all should unite without any envy. Robbers and other law breakers should be identified and driven away. Punishment is to be ensured those who deserve it. There is voice of togetherness in the sayings of Kashyapa though the casteism is recognized as a system. There is separate section on collection of agricultural impediments. Prayers and offerings are to be submitted to the impediments also to the earth.

*Bhumidevi namste/stu mahi sarvamsahe/adhuna
 Krishyarambham karishyami prasanna bhava suvrathe
 Karshanam thadanam yaccha tvayi yadyadkritham maya
 Devi kshamasva that sarvam kuru mahyam mahaphalam
 Tvam eva matha sarvesham praninamiha keerthyathe
 Atha prasanna bhudevi phalam dehyamatham kshithau*

(Oh! Goddess Earth, I prostrate before you. You are omniscient. I am to begin the activity of cultivation. Kindly be pleased. Pardon my tilling and ploughing. All are to be fruitful. You are the mother of all living beings. So, be pleased and provide all the fruits.)

Worship is also offered to the buffaloes.

Elaboration of ideal features of cow and buffalo is a very interesting part. Selection of the best possible field for cultivation, methods of collection of seeds, ploughing before sowing the seeds; are the subjects of subsequent chapters. Cultivation is not limited to cereals alone. Several other varieties necessary for a civilized society such as pigeon pea, horse gram, chick pea, black gram, sesame, mustard, cumin sugarcane, banana, brinjal, turmeric, ginger, cotton etc. are also detailed with appropriate seasons and methods.

Bhojya-abhojya-krama-kathanam is a guideline for what is to be eaten and what not. The customs related to food are reflected in this part. For example, foods to be avoided by Brahmins are narrated. This portion deals with the preparation havya (food offered in sacrifices) and nivedana (prepared food offered in oblation)

Sharngadharapaddhathi

Text of VA popular in Kerala, is a portion with this subject taken from Sharngadhara-padhathi, an encyclopedic work written by Sharngadhara (14th Cen.). It was first published in 1945. It was in Malayalam script with an introduction reputed scholar Sri. Shooranadu Kujan Pillai. Newer edition with an English translation was published in 2022. There are eleven chapters with an appendix. The first chapter bhumi-pareeksha analyses the land and types of soil. Those ideal for plant growth are identified. Procedure of sowing of seeds is the content of second chapter. Processing the seed is very important. Propagation of a plant is seed, stem or tuber. Which

one related to each plant is described in the third chapter. Steps in planting of the tree sapling with ideal location, proper irrigation are followed in next chapters. Poshana-vidhi is the chapter on different manures needed for plants. Treatment of the diseases of plants narrated in the eighth chapter. As in human, identification of body constitution, based on dosha- theory is highlighted here. Auspiciousness with divinity of plants is the focus of a separate chapter. In upavanaprakriya how to make garden is well illustrated. Chithreekarana is added as an appendix. Here, the techniques to manipulate the the colour, size etc. of flower, fruit, mode of growth of a plant. It can be called botanical marvels.

Upavanavinoda of Madanapala, mostly follows VA in Sharngadhara-paddhathi.

Krishiparashara is another unique book. Opening verse suggests that the work belongs to sage Parashara. Importance of agriculture is praised in the introductory chapter. Vrishti-khanta basically postulates a system for forecasting rains. Identifying the type of clouds is very significant for this. The planetary positions favoring rain each month is also described. Equally important is the features of anavrishti (lack or absence of rains). The portion krishi-khanda begins with cattle bearing which is closely related to any agricultural activity. Constructing plough is narrated in detail and auspicious days and time for initial use is also mentioned. Sowing, removal of weeds, irrigation, harvesting, collection and storage the harvest are the other relevant contents of the book. Many these activities are linked to rituals.

Conclusion

Analysis of ancient Indian literature clearly shows the gradual genesis of VA from the Vedic periods itself. There was a continuous but steady development, throughout various centuries. During this period, exclusive texts on VA were also written. It is not easy to fix the exact dates of different texts for obvious reasons. Further literary studies are necessary for mining out the total information available in this knowledge system. These can also contribute much to the socio-cultural history of our country. Researches in this VA surely

will unveil the methodology with which the system progressed. The scope of these practices, in current era is also to be explored.

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KIRANĀVALĪ

Journal of Sanskrit Research Foundation

The New Trivandrum Sanskrit Series Vol. XVI. Book I-IV

January - December 2024

ISSN 0975-4067

Printed and published by: Dr.C.S.Sasikumar, Secretary, Sanskrit Research Foundation, Thiruvananthapuram, for Sanskrit Research Foundation,